

Influence of Nitrogen Doping and Pre-Carbonization on the Performance of Lignin-Derived Activated Carbon for Supercapacitor Applications

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Nanostructured carbons are widely used as active materials for supercapacitor applications owing to their high specific surface area and electrical conductivity. Biomass waste-derived materials can be sustainably produced. In this work, highly porous activated carbon was prepared from lignin waste for supercapacitor applications, and the effects of nitrogen doping and a pre-carbonization treatment on the final performance were investigated. Particularly, activated carbonized lignin (ACL) and activated lignin (AL) samples were prepared with or without a pre-carbonization step, respectively, and with or without nitrogen doping. Nitrogen doping of the samples was found to decrease the capacitance owing to the loss of critical oxygen-

containing functional groups, which provide pseudocapacitance. Meanwhile, the use of a pre-carbonization treatment greatly improved the surface area and capacitance of the materials. Sorptometry analysis indicated that ACL and AL have high specific surface areas of 3174 and 2289 m² g⁻¹, respectively. ACL achieved a specific capacitance of 306.4 F g⁻¹ and 292.1 F g⁻¹ in 1 mol L⁻¹ KOH and H₂SO₄, respectively. Furthermore, the contribution of a pre-carbonization treatment to improve the surface area and maintain the presence of oxygen-containing functional groups was identified as beneficial towards improving the pseudocapacitance properties of the porous carbon materials.

1. Introduction

Supercapacitors are electrochemical energy storage devices that store electrical charge by electrical double-layer capacitance (EDLC) or pseudocapacitance mechanisms.^[1] Pseudocapacitance is achieved through Faradic reactions of redox-active materials, including transition metal oxides,^[2-4] organic redox-active molecules,^[5-7] or conductive polymers.^[8,9] Meanwhile, EDLC stores charge through rapid adsorption and desorption of ions from the electrolyte onto an electrode surface via electrostatic interactions.^[1,10] Electrical double-layer capacitors are typically electrochemically stable, predominantly composed of conductive and high-surface-area nanostructured carbon materials:^[11,12] carbon nanotubes (CNTs),^[13,14] graphene,^[15] or activated carbons.^[16,17] However, the preparation of nanostructured

carbon materials can require costly and complicated production processes that include the usage of toxic chemicals.^[18,19] For example, the preparation of graphene oxide via the Hummer's method^[20] utilizes KMnO₄, a very strong oxidizing agent, as well as concentrated H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄.^[20-24] In the global push towards sustainability and the pursuit of a circular economy, the cost-effective production of nanostructured carbon materials for energy storage applications using sustainable precursor sources such as biomass from industry sectors is critical.^[25] Yet, the large-scale utilization of biomass-derived materials is limited by high surface area and porosity requirements to increase the energy storage capacities and maintain electrochemical stability.

Lignin is an amorphous polymer that is present in waste produced from agricultural and pulp/paper processes. Globally, about 70 million tons of lignin are generated annually during the extraction of cellulose for the paper industry.^[27-30] The low-cost and renewable nature make lignin an attractive material for various applications, yet large-scale conversion of lignin into value-added products has not been widely implemented. Less than 2% of the total global production of lignin is used for purposes such as stabilizing agents, concrete additives, or surfactants.^[26,31] The majority of extracted lignin is either discarded as waste or burned as a low-quality fuel. Conversely, the advantageous features of lignin, including high carbon content, widespread availability, thermal stability, and biodegradability, allow for the opportunity to utilize lignin in more value-added applications, such as precursors to prepare electrode materials for supercapacitors.^[32,33] However, processing of biomass materials such as lignin and identifying the optimal conditions to produce materials with desirable properties for supercapacitor applications is worthy of investigation.

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Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under <https://doi.org/10.1002/slct.202404561>

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Lignin can be converted into activated carbon by using physical or chemical techniques.^[26,34] There are several considerations when determining the best route toward developing activated carbon from lignin. An area of significant research interest is the investigation of the activator that facilitates the chemical activation process and determines the porosity and surface area of the final carbon materials. Chemical activators react with the carbon matrix and create additional porosity during the thermochemical activation process. Wu et al.^[47] demonstrated the influence of activators on the electrochemical performance of lignin-based supercapacitors. Zhang et al. investigated the role of activation temperature and KOH/carbon ratio on the resulting specific surface area of lignin-derived supercapacitor materials. The optimal conditions were at a KOH/carbon ratio of 4:1 and activation temperature of 800 °C that resulted in materials with a surface area of 3775 m² g⁻¹ and a specific capacitance of 286.7 F g⁻¹ at 0.2 A g⁻¹ in 6 mol L⁻¹ KOH.^[35] Li et al. studied the influence of hydrothermal carbonization pretreatment before the activation step on the properties of hierarchical porous carbon structures, where they reported a specific surface area of 1504 m² g⁻¹ and a specific capacitance of 324 F g⁻¹ at 0.5 A g⁻¹ in 6 mol L⁻¹ KOH.^[36]

While significant work has been done on the influence of activators, other aspects of the treatment process can be further investigated. Heteroatom doping with elements like nitrogen, oxygen, boron, and/or sulfur has been reported to enhance supercapacitor carbon materials by reducing charge transfer resistance through the creation of active sites and providing pseudocapacitive properties.^[26,37] Particularly, nitrogen has a role as an *n*-type, electron-donating dopant that promotes electron transfer to carbon molecules in the substrate.^[38,39] For example, Plavniece et al. used wood and black liquor waste to thermochemically produce activated carbon for energy storage applications. Then, they used dicyandiamide to N-dope the activated carbon and reported improved performance compared to commercial 20% Pt/C when used as an oxygen reduction catalyst and as anode materials in Li-ion batteries. They showed that nitrogen doping reduces the charge transfer resistance of materials, which is an important factor in supercapacitor electrodes.^[38] In another study, Tamasauskaite-Tamasiunaite et al. used black liquor and wood char-based nitrogen-doped activated carbon for supercapacitor electrode materials. They reported a high specific surface area of 2690 m² g⁻¹ for the mixture of black liquor and wood charcoal sample. This N-doped activated carbon electrode showed a specific capacitance of 142 F g⁻¹ at 0.2 A g⁻¹ in 1 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄.^[39] Nitrogen-doped carbon materials offer advantages in specific applications. For instance, nitrogen doping can reduce the restacking of graphene structures and enhance the interaction of the carbon-based substrate with redox-active organic molecules.^[40] However, when it comes to biomass-derived activated carbon, a complex scenario unfolds. The quinone functionalities in lignin exhibit their own redox activity. This presents a dilemma: nitrogen doping can improve certain properties, but it may also lead to the loss of valuable redox-active quinone moieties inherent in lignin-based materials.^[41] Consequently, the benefits of nitrogen doping must be carefully weighed against its potential drawbacks. To fully understand the effects of nitrogen doping on the structure and

functionality of lignin-based materials, systematic studies are essential.

In this work, we investigate the impact of nitrogen doping and the use of a low-temperature pre-carbonization step, in which a lignin-based precursor is heated to 400 °C for 4.5 h under Ar on the surface area and electrochemical supercapacitance of lignin-derived activated carbon materials. Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) analysis calculated the specific surface area of non-precarbonized and precarbonized samples to be 2289.3 and 3174.5 m² g⁻¹, respectively. The electrodes prepared with a pre-carbonization step but no nitrogen doping, ACL, achieved 95% capacitance retention after 5000 CV cycles and the highest capacitances of 292.1 F g⁻¹ and 306.4 F g⁻¹ in 1 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ and KOH electrolytes, respectively, which were significantly higher than some of the reported values for graphene and its derivatives in similar electrolytes.^[42] Nitrogen doping resulted in smaller specific surface areas and the loss of key oxygen-containing functionalities in the samples compared to undoped samples and, consequently, lower Faradaic capacitances. In addition, an ACL electrode showed a power density of 501.3 W kg⁻¹ and an energy density of 7.7 W h kg⁻¹ at 0.5 A g⁻¹ in a symmetric supercapacitor. This promising performance of the lignin-derived electrodes presented in this work is due to their highly porous structure and good electrical conductivity, which indicates their potential to act as a sustainable and cost-effective alternative to other nanostructured carbon materials such as graphene or CNTs.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials

Hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, sodium hydroxide, sodium bicarbonate, *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), dicyandiamide, ethanol, and Nafion 117-containing solution (5 wt% in a mixture of lower aliphatic alcohols and water) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). All solutions were prepared using Type 1 ultrapure water (>18 MΩ cm, Millipore, USA).

2.2. Preparation of Lignin-Derived Activated Carbon and Nitrogen-Doped Activated Carbon

Activated lignin (AL) samples were prepared using lignin sourced from Fibenol, an Estonian biorefinery. Lignin precursor was mixed with NaOH (1:3 raw material/NaOH) and then activated for 2 h at 700 °C under Ar flow (yield ~12%). After the activation, samples were demineralized by refluxing in 10% HCl for 2 h, washed with deionized water until a neutral pH was achieved, and dried at 60 °C overnight. The obtained powder was named activated lignin (AL). In order to dope AL samples with nitrogen (nitrogen-doped (N-AL)), AL was mixed with dicyandiamide in DMF. The excess DMF was removed using a rotary evaporator. Then, the AL and dicyandiamide mixture was annealed at 800 °C under Ar in order to facilitate nitrogen-doping.

Activated carbonized lignin (ACL) samples were prepared using lignin sourced from Fibenol. The lignin precursor underwent a pre-carbonization treatment at 400 °C for 270 min under Ar flow (53% yield), then mixed with NaOH at a 1:3 carbonizate to NaOH ratio and activated for 2 h at 700 °C in Ar flow (30% yield). After the

activation, samples were demineralized by refluxing in 10% HCl for 2 h and then washed with deionized water until a neutral pH was achieved. Demineralization was followed by drying at 60 °C overnight. The obtained black powder was named ACL. For preparing the nitrogen-doped activated carbonized lignin (N-ACL), ACL was used as a precursor, and the same procedure as for preparing N-AL samples was followed.

2.3. Physical Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL7000F), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), and electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS) mapping (Talos 200X) were used to investigate the morphology and distribution of elements of the samples. The specific surface areas and pore size distributions of the samples were evaluated using nitrogen sorption at 77 K (Quantachrome Nova 4200 K) isotherms applying Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) and density functional theory (DFT) analyses, respectively. DFT is commonly used to calculate pore size in micro- and mesopore containing materials because it accurately models the molecular interactions between gas molecules and the walls of the micro- and mesopores. This detailed analysis captures the unique adsorption behaviors within small pores. Elemental analysis was performed using the Elementar Unicube instrument. The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were conducted to investigate the near-surface elemental composition of the performance materials by employing the Scienta SES100 hemispherical analyzer (pass energy = 200 eV) and non-monochromated Mg K α exciting radiation from a XR-4 twin anode X-ray source (Thermo VG Scientific).

2.4. Electrochemical Evaluation

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge/discharge (GCD) measurements were used to investigate the electrochemical behavior of samples using a Biologic VSP-300 potentiostat. The electrochemical experiments were performed in a 3-electrode electrochemical cell, where Ag/AgCl was used as the reference electrode and a graphite rod as the counter electrode. The working electrode was prepared by drop-casting 5 μ L of an ink dispersion containing the active material to achieve an electrode loading of 25 μ g cm $^{-2}$. The ink was prepared by mixing 2 mg of active material, 2 mL of ethanol, and 60 μ L of Nafion 117-containing solution (5 wt% in a mixture of lower aliphatic alcohols and water) followed by ultrasonication for 1 h. The electrolytes were prepared with 1 mol L $^{-1}$ Na $_2$ SO $_4$ for the neutral electrolyte, 1 mol L $^{-1}$ KOH for the alkaline electrolyte, and 1 mol L $^{-1}$ H $_2$ SO $_4$ for the acidic electrolyte.

Equation 1^[43] was used to calculate specific capacitance from cyclic voltammetry (C_{cv}).

$$C_{cv} = \frac{\int IdV}{2\beta \Delta Vm} \quad (1)$$

where I is the current, v is the scan rate, m is the mass of active materials, and ΔV is the working potential window. Equation 2^[43] was used to calculate the specific capacitance from the galvanostatic charge/discharge (C_s , GCD) profile.

$$C_{GCD} = \frac{I}{(dV/dt)m} \quad (2)$$

where dV/dt is the slope of the discharge curve.

Furthermore, the performance of the prepared active materials was also tested in a symmetrical CR3032 coin cell. An ink prepared as described above was drop-casted onto carbon paper (1.26 cm 2

Table 1. The porous structure information of the ACL, N-ACL, AL, and N-AL.

Material	Specific Surface Area (BET) (m 2 g $^{-1}$)	Total Pore Volume (Vt) (cm 3 g $^{-1}$)	Micropore Volume (cm 3 g $^{-1}$)	Micropore from Vt (%)	Average Pore Width (nm)
ACL	3175	1.69	1.00	59.2	2.14
N-ACL	2984	1.52	0.93	61.2	2.11
AL	2289	1.27	0.78	61.4	2.21
N-AL	1977	1.17	0.64	54.7	2.37

of geometrical surface area) to achieve an active material loading of 7.5 mg cm $^{-2}$ on the carbon paper. A glass fiber separator (grade GF/D, Whatman) impregnated with electrolyte solution was placed between the two electrodes. This symmetrical supercapacitor was tested under a voltage window of 1 V using GCD at different current densities of 0.5, 1, 5, 10, and 20 A g $^{-1}$ and CV at different scan rates 50, 25, and 5 mV s $^{-1}$. The electrolyte that led to the highest capacitances in each material in initial 3-electrode experiments was chosen for coin cell tests. Furthermore, the stability of coin cells was evaluated using GCD at 0.5 A g $^{-1}$ current density.

Equations 3 and 4^[43] were used to calculate the energy and power density of the symmetric supercapacitor:

$$\text{Energy density } (E) = \frac{\Delta V^2 \times C_{sp} \times 1000}{2 \times 3600} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Power density } (P) = \frac{E}{\Delta t} \quad (4)$$

Here, ΔV is the operating cell voltage, C_{sp} is the specific capacitance of the electrode, and Δt is the discharge time in seconds.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Physical Characterization

The specific surface area of AL, ACL, N-AL, and N-ACL was calculated based on the results of BET measurements. A summary of the specific surface areas and pore structures for all samples is presented in Table 1. The specific surface areas of ACL and AL were 3174.5 and 2289.4 m 2 g $^{-1}$, respectively, which were significantly higher than the nitrogen-doped samples with specific surface areas of 2984 and 1977 m 2 g $^{-1}$ for N-ACL and N-AL, respectively. This indicates that the nitrogen doping process resulted in decreasing the specific surface area of the samples. The heat treatment of dicyandiamide/activated carbon at 800 °C was at a higher temperature than the activation process (700 °C). The dicyandiamide precursor during this pyrolysis step will likely carbonize, causing blockage or coverage of some of the pores that initially existed in the activated carbon, thereby leading to a reduced surface area of the ACL and AL versus N-ACL and N-AL, respectively, as well as the incorporation of nitrogen into the final material structure. The aforementioned results show the production of highly porous carbon-based materials by using a sequence of carbonization and activation steps. The carbonization step proved to increase the micropore volume, as expected

Figure 1. (a) N_2 adsorption–desorption isotherms and (b) pore size distribution of the ACL, N-ACL, AL, and N-AL.

with the literature.^[38,44,45] The calculated average pore size (DFT method) was 2.14, 2.11, 2.21, and 2.37 nm for ACL, N-ACL, AL, and N-AL, respectively. The total pore volume is also larger in the carbonized samples, with 1.53 and 1.42 $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$ for ACL and N-ACL, respectively. Meanwhile, samples prepared without carbonizations had a total pore volume of 1.15 and 1.07 $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$ for AL and N-AL, respectively. The pore size distribution of the samples is presented in Figure 1b.

The nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms of all four samples prepared in this work (AL, N-AL, ACL, and N-ACL) are shown in Figure 1a. The lack of significant hysteresis in the range of relative pressures from 0.2 to 0.9 indicates the presence of mesopores demonstrating the predominance of micropores in the ACL and N-ACL samples.^[38,39] Results presented in Figure 1a,b and Table 1 revealed that materials prepared with a pre-carbonization step before activation adsorb nitrogen more readily, thereby having higher pore volume compared to the AL samples, which were prepared without pre-carbonization. It should be noted that the pre-carbonized samples after activation have not only higher total pore volumes (ACL at 1.69 and AL at 1.27 $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$), but also higher micropore volumes (ACL at 1.00 and AL at 0.78 $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$) compared to AL, resulting in higher specific surface areas. BET analysis of the surface area and nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherm tests concludes that carbonization as a pretreatment step is critical to developing materials with extensive microporous structures and high surface areas.

In order to investigate the role of nitrogen-doping on pseudocapacitance properties, the samples were doped with nitrogen at 800 °C. By treating the samples at a temperature higher than the activation temperature of 700 °C, the micropore walls collapse, forming larger pores, thereby decreasing the specific surface area. Also, it has been reported that annealing at 800 °C provides materials with high content of pyridinic, pyrrolic, and quaternary groups.^[39]

SEM and TEM images of samples ACL, N-ACL, AL, and N-AL are presented in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. N-ACL (Figure 2b) and N-AL (Figure 2d) have large particles compared to ACL (Figure 2a) and AL (Figure 2c), which were nitrogen-doped and appear to contain smaller particles. The porous structure of all samples can also be seen in the TEM images (TEM images with lower resolution are shown in Figure S1). Furthermore, EELS was used to investigate the elemental distributions of the ACL, N-ACL, AL, and N-AL, which are presented in Figure S2 for ACL

Sample	C (at.%)	O (at.%)	N (at.%)
ACL	95.5	4.5	–
N-ACL	96.5	0.6	2.9
AL	92.7	7.3	–
N-AL	93.4	2.7	3.9

and N-ACL and Figure S3 for AL and N-AL. Samples were mostly composed of carbon. Nitrogen was also detected throughout the structures of N-ACL and N-AL samples, indicating uniform distribution of nitrogen from the doping procedure.

XPS analysis was used to investigate the near-surface atomic composition of the samples, with the results presented in Table 2 and survey spectra displayed in Figure 4 for all samples. The carbon content of the samples was relatively constant in the range of 95–96.5 at.% for ACL and 92–93.5 at.% for AL samples. The N1s peak could only be observed in the N-ACL and N-AL survey spectra, indicating that nitrogen-doping was successful and in agreement with the EELS results. The high-resolution N1s spectra of N-ACL and N-AL are shown in Figure 4a,b. Four distinct components corresponding to graphitic-N (400.6 eV), pyrrolic-N (399.5 eV), pyridinic-N (398.1 eV), and pyridine-N-oxide (402.2 eV) were observed in the spectra.^[41] The latter three N-groups have been reported as redox-active species,^[7,42] which can increase the energy storage potential of the material. The oxygen content of ACL and AL samples were 4.5% and 7.3%, respectively, which were higher than the oxygen content of N-ACL (0.6%) and N-AL (2.7%), indicating the loss of oxygen-containing groups during the N-doping process. In the high-resolution O1s spectra of the samples in Figure 4c–f, three peaks could be observed in all of the samples that could be attributed to carbonyl (C=O; 530.8 eV), C–O in epoxy and hydroxyl (C–OH/C–O–C; 532.3 eV), and carboxylic acid functional groups (O=C–O; 533.5 eV), which have also been reported to be redox-active species.^[41] Furthermore, elemental analysis was used to provide additional insight into the elemental composition of the samples. The results (Table S1) showed a similar elemental composition to those measured by XPS, with a 0–0.5 at.% difference for each element determined between the two techniques. This variation may be attributed

Figure 2. SEM images of (a) ACL, (b) N-ACL, (c) AL, and (d) N-AL.

Figure 3. HRTEM images of (a) ACL, (b) N-ACL, (c) AL, and (d) N-AL.

Figure 4. XPS high-resolution N1 s spectra of (a) N-ACL and (b) N-AL. The high-resolution O1 s spectra of (c) ACL, (d) N-ACL, (e) AL, and (f) N-AL.

to the fact that XPS is a near-surface technique, while elemental analysis provides bulk composition information.

3.2. Electrochemical Evaluation

Cyclic voltammetry was performed to evaluate the electrochemical performance of AL, ACL, N-AL, and N-ACL in three different electrolytes: 1 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄, 1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH, and 1 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ with the results collected at a scan rate of 50 mVs⁻¹ shown in Figure 4. The specific capacitance was calculated by Equation 1, using the results of CV measurements, and are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of specific capacitance of different samples in acidic, alkaline, and neutral electrolytes at 50 mV s⁻¹.

Sample	Specific Capacitance (F g ⁻¹)			SSA (BET) (m ² g ⁻¹)	O (at.%)
	H ₂ SO ₄	Na ₂ SO ₄	KOH		
ACL	292.1	168.7	306.4	3175	4.5
N-ACL	270.4	147.9	291.7	2984	0.6
AL	286.0	175.3	294.7	2289	7.3
N-AL	241.7	108.1	241.7	1977	2.7

In 1 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ electrolyte, ACL achieved the highest capacitance of the samples with a specific capacitance of 292.1 F

g^{-1} , followed by AL, N-ACL, and N-AL with 286.0, 270.4, and 241.7 F g^{-1} , respectively. In 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 electrolyte, AL achieved the highest capacitance of 175.3 F g^{-1} , followed by ACL, N-ACL, and N-AL, showing 168.7, 147.9, and 108.1 F g^{-1} , respectively. In KOH electrolyte, ACL achieved the highest capacitance at 306.4 F g^{-1} , followed by AL, N-ACL, and N-AL, with 294.7, 291.7, and 241.7 F g^{-1} , respectively. The promising performance of all samples may be due to the higher specific surface area and the presence of both extensive micropore and mesopore features in the samples prepared in this work.

As described above, in 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 and KOH electrolyte, ACL showed the highest capacitance, which may be a result of the higher measured surface area among the samples. However, in neutral media, AL showed the highest capacitance. Although the specific surface area of AL (2289 m^2g^{-1}) is lower than ACL (3174 m^2g^{-1}), the higher capacitance could be due to its larger micropore to mesopore ratio. The pore size distributions and ratio of micro- and mesopores in the overall structure can affect the performance of the electrode materials. Mesopores with sizes of 2–50 nm can act as transport channels for ions through the structure of the electrode during the processes of charge and discharge, and as a result, their presence leads to a decrease in the ionic transport resistance of the supercapacitors.^[38,39] Micropores up to 2 nm in size, accessible to electrolyte ions, can provide high capacitive characteristics of the material. Both macropores and large mesopores can function as buffer reservoirs, reducing the ion diffusion distance.^[44] The ratio of micropores to mesopores is also a critical factor in defining the conductivity and the performance of the electrode material. We believe that a combination of mesopores and micropores in the ACL and AL samples has resulted in achieving a high specific capacitance for neutral electrolytes, which require larger pore sizes as the ions are larger when compared to the OH^- and H^+ ions that facilitate electron transfer in the basic and acidic electrolytes, respectively.

XPS analysis showed that the oxygen content of ACL and AL was significantly higher than N-ACL and N-AL. The pseudocapacitive behavior observed in the CV curves of AL and ACL in 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 shown in Figure 5a could be attributed to the presence of the quinone/hydroquinone redox couple. After nitrogen doping, the increased nitrogen content of the samples (N-ACL and N-AL) reduced the oxygen content, resulting in lowered pseudocapacitive features of the CV curves for N-ACL and N-AL, agreeing with the results reported previously.^[41] These results indicate that electrical double-layer capacitance is the dominant storage mechanism, and no significant contribution of pseudocapacitance was observed in the nitrogen-doped samples. Besides, specific capacitances of N-ACL and N-AL are lower than the corresponding undoped samples, ACL and AL, respectively, in all electrolytes (Figure 5b). The nitrogen-doping process also decreased the specific surface area, which has a negative effect on the performance of N-ACL and N-AL as electrodes.

The stability of the ACL was evaluated in 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 and 1 M KOH, while the stability of AL was tested in 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 because these samples achieved the highest capacitance

in these electrolyte conditions. Stability tests were performed by completing 5000 CV cycles at 100 mV s^{-1} using a 3-electrode electrochemical cell. The results are presented in Figures S5 and S6. Capacitance retention of ACL in 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 in 1 M KOH was 93.9% and 94.2%, respectively, after 5000 CV cycles. The stability of AL was tested in 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 , over 5000 CV cycles, and AL maintained 98.6% of its maximum capacitance. It is noteworthy that AL capacitance increased during the initial cycles. The slight increase in capacitance could be due to the larger size of ions in the Na_2SO_4 and the lower pore volume of AL, which require a longer time for diffusion to the electrode structure.

Based on the results from three-electrode cell measurements, sample ACL in 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 and 1 mol L^{-1} KOH, and sample AL in 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 were subjected to performance evaluation in a symmetric supercapacitor using a coin cell. These supercapacitors were tested at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} with an electrode loading of 7.5 mg cm^{-2} . In 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 and 1 mol L^{-1} KOH, ACL demonstrated specific capacitances of 55.3 and 45.5 F g^{-1} , power densities of 501.3 and 498.5 W kg^{-1} , and energy densities of 7.7 and 6.3 Wh kg^{-1} , respectively. In 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 , AL exhibited a specific capacitance of 52 F g^{-1} , a power density of 500.2 W kg^{-1} , and an energy density of 7.2 Wh kg^{-1} . Performance descriptors for the different coin cells are summarized in Table S2, and the CV curves and GCD profiles are shown in Figure 5c,d. In Figure 5c, ACL exhibited only electrical double-layer capacitance (EDLC), indicating that the pseudocapacitive behavior observed in the three-electrode system disappeared in the two-electrode system with higher active material loading. The GCD profiles were triangular in shape, further confirming EDLC as the only charge storage mechanism.

The effect of material porosity on electrochemical performance was studied using CV at slow scan rates (5 and 25 mV s^{-1}). The CV profiles (Figure S7) revealed that AL in 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 showed a significant increase in specific capacitance, from 93.4 F g^{-1} at 25 mV s^{-1} to 122.4 F g^{-1} at 5 mV s^{-1} , compared to ACL in both 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 and 1 mol L^{-1} KOH. This higher increase in capacitance may be attributed to the larger ion size of Na_2SO_4 , as slower scan rates allow the electrolyte more time to diffuse into the electrode pores, benefiting capacitance improvement for larger ions. The rate capability of the coin cells was evaluated using GCD at various current densities (0.5, 1, 5, 10, and 20 A g^{-1}), with results shown in Figure S8. ACL retained 40.1% and 26.4% of its initial capacitance as the current density increased from 1 to 20 A g^{-1} in 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 and 1 mol L^{-1} KOH, respectively. In contrast, AL lost 90% of its initial capacitance over the same current range in 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 . Cycling stability was investigated at 0.5 A g^{-1} over 5000 cycles, with results presented in Figure S9. ACL retained 82% and 73% of its initial capacitance in 1 mol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 and 1 mol L^{-1} KOH, respectively, while AL maintained 70% of its initial capacitance in 1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 . The performance of these electrodes could be further enhanced in asymmetric coin cells by pairing pseudocapacitive materials with those exhibiting high EDLC. Additionally, a comparative analysis with similar biomass-based materials is provided in Table S4.

Figure 5. 3-Electrode electrochemical measurements, including (a) cyclic voltammetry of samples in 1 M H₂SO₄ and (b) 1 M KOH at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. Symmetric coin cell measurements with a 7.5 mg cm⁻² loading, including (c) cyclic voltammetry at 50 mV s⁻¹ and (d) galvanostatic charge/discharge at 1 A g⁻¹ of ACL in 1 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ and (b) 1 mol L⁻¹ KOH, and AL in 1 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄.

4. Conclusions

Activated carbons were prepared by the pyrolysis of lignin-based waste at 700 °C as highly porous electrode materials for supercapacitor applications. The effect of nitrogen doping and a pre-carbonization treatment was investigated on electrode performance as supercapacitors in KOH, Na₂SO₄, and H₂SO₄ electrolytes. Sorptometry measurements indicated that nitrogen doping has resulted in lowering the specific surface area of the samples, while the pre-carbonization treatment increased the specific surface area. The specific surface of ACL and AL were 3174.5 and 2289.3 m² g⁻¹, while the specific surface area of N-ACL and N-AL, which were nitrogen-doped samples, were 2894.2 and 1977.4 m² g⁻¹, respectively. ACL showed the highest specific capacitance 292.1 F g⁻¹ in H₂SO₄ and 306.4 F g⁻¹ in KOH, meanwhile, AL achieved the highest specific capacitance, 195.3 F g⁻¹ in Na₂SO₄. XPS and EELS analysis determined that the nitrogen-doping process removed oxygen-containing quinone moieties in the materials, which further reduced the capacitances of these samples. Overall, the electrodes showed higher capacitances in H₂SO₄ and KOH media compared to the Na₂SO₄, which was attributed to the higher ionic conductivity and smaller ion sizes in these electrolytes.^[46] Furthermore, the performances of the electrodes were evaluated in symmetric supercapacitors using coin cells. ACL achieved 501.3 W kg⁻¹ power density and 7.7 Wh kg⁻¹ energy density in 1 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ and 498.5 W kg⁻¹ power density and 6.3 Wh kg⁻¹ energy density

in 1 mol L⁻¹ KOH. AL showed 500.2 W kg⁻¹ power density and 7.2 Wh kg⁻¹ energy density in 1 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄. ACL showed capacitance retention of approximately 95% in acidic and alkaline, respectively, after 5000 charge/discharge cycles, while the specific capacitance of AL dropped less than 2% over 5000 CV cycles and could maintain 98.6% of the maximum capacitance value. The biomass-derived approach has been demonstrated as an effective route to produce materials that can either be used as active materials in supercapacitors directly or leveraged for use as supports for pseudocapacitive materials, including redox-active organic molecules, conductive polymers, or transition metal oxides to increase the specific capacitance and improve the power density and energy density of the supercapacitor electrode.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), the Alliance International Catalyst program, and the McMaster University Faculty of Engineering. Electron microscopy was performed at the Canadian Centre for Electron Microscopy (CEM). The research was also funded by the project "Sustainably Produced Carbon Nanomaterials for Energy Applications (SuNaMa)," which benefits from a € 988,000 grant from Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway through the EEA Grants (project contract with the Research Council of

Lithuania (LMTLT) No. is S-BMT-21-12 (LT08-2-LMT-K-01-055)), and by the Ministry of Education and Research through the Centre of Excellence in Circular Economy for Strategic Mineral and Carbon Resources (01.01.2024–31.12.2030, TK228).

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: Electrical double-layer capacitance · Lignin-based material · Nitrogen doping · Pre-carbonization · Supercapacitors

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Manuscript received: September 24, 2024